

The Open Access Game - Université de Bordeaux: summary leaflet of questions and additional answers

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Introduction

This leaflet brings together by topic all the questions and answers of the Open Access Game - Université de Bordeaux. The game description and all associated files are available online, published under the [Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 license](#).

Flamerie, F. & Bahroun, N. (2023). The Open Access Game / Le jeu du libre accès - Université de Bordeaux. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7844554>

Open access journals

11 questions prefixed JOUR

JOUR-01: When a researcher publishes an open access article, the publisher asks to cover the publication costs by paying APCs (Article Processing Charges):

- A) Always
- B) Often
- C) Never

Correct answer : B) Often

Payment of APCs by the author or his/her institution is common but not systematic, as many open access journals are funded through other mechanisms.

JOUR-02: You can receive funds from Inserm or the University of Bordeaux to cover your open access publication costs.

Organization-specific question

Correct answer : FALSE

Some institutions have set up a fund to support Open Access publishing, but this is not the case for Inserm nor the University of Bordeaux. However both have concluded agreements with certain publishers allowing for a complete or partial exemption from the APC.

JOUR-03: For the year 2020, what is the estimated total amount of APCs paid by French institutions?

- A) Less than 10 million euros
- B) Between 10 and 25 million euros
- C) More than 25 million euros

Correct answer : C) More than 25 million euros

30.1 million euros... plus 87.5 million euros in subscription expenses!

Source : Blanchard, A., Thierry, D., & Graaf, M. van der. (2022). Retrospective and prospective study of the evolution of APC costs and electronic subscriptions for French institutions. Comité pour la science ouverte. <https://doi.org/10.52949/26>

JOUR-04: How much are the APCs for the publication of an article in BMC Public Health?

Organization-specific question

- A) Less than 2'000 euros
- B) Between 2'000 and 5'000 euros
- C) More than 5'000 euros

Correct answer : B) Between 2'000 and 5'000 euros

For BMC Public Health, the public amount of APCs is €2'890. For an example of A) < 2000€ let's consider PeerJ at \$1'795 ; PLoS One and most other mega-journals are now over €2000. For an example of C) > €5,000, Lancet Global Health will cost \$5'780, with a 10% discount from the beginning of 2024 thanks to the national license with Elsevier.

JOUR-05: Can you publish open access in Nature an article related to an ANR or Horizon Europe project?

Correct answer : TRUE

Note that you will not be able to use the project budget to fund this expense. Nature is a hybrid journal and APCs in this type of journal are no longer eligible expenses.

JOUR-06: A hybrid journal is...

- A) A former subscription journal transformed into an open access journal
- B) A subscription journal containing open access articles
- C) A journal available in both print and electronic formats

Correct answer : B) A subscription journal containing open access articles

Funding agencies now generally refuse to cover the costs of publishing in hybrid journals. APCs are generally higher in hybrid journals than in fully open access journals.

JOUR-07: Some journals mix open access articles with gated articles.

Correct answer : TRUE

These journals are "hybrid journals".

JOUR-08: Articles published in open access journals do not go through the peer review system.

Correct answer : FALSE

Open access journals work like traditional journals from this point of view.

JOUR-09: What are the criteria for identifying a predatory journal?

- A) Very fast publication times (less than a week) guaranteed
- B) Very high APCs
- C) Unclear peer review process

Correct answer : A) Very fast publication times (less than a week) guaranteed and C) Unclear peer review process

Actually, predatory journals often charge low APCs.

JOUR-10: An open access journal is of lower quality than a subscription journal.

Correct answer : FALSE

The business model of the journal (subscription or open access) is not linked to the quality of the content.

JOUR-11: Which of the following sites can be used to ensure the quality of an open access journal?

- A) DOAJ
- B) PubMed
- C) QUOAM
- D) Sherpa/Romeo

Correct answer : A) DOAJ - Directory of open access journals and C) QUOAM - Quality of open access marker

Indexing by bibliographic databases such as PubMed is not a sufficient criterion to ensure the quality of a journal. Sherpa/Romeo aggregates publishers' copyright and open access archiving policies on a journal-by-journal basis.

Open access repositories

10 questions prefixed REP

REP-01: To deposit an article in the Oskar open access repository, all information must be entered manually.

Organization-specific question

Correct answer : FALSE

The majority of the information can be retrieved from the article's DOI or PMID.

REP-02: In the Oskar open access repository, you can find all the publications of your team on a specific web page.

Organization-specific question

Correct answer : TRUE

All the bibliographic references of BPH members' articles are deposited into Oskar from an extraction from the publication database maintained by the BPH documentation centre. Information about research teams is included in this monthly export and used in Oskar.

REP-03: What is an embargo for a scientific publication?

- A) The period during which an article cannot be freely accessed
- B) The prohibition to pay the authors of an article
- C) An article whose publication is forbidden

Correct answer : A) The period during which an article cannot be freely accessed

The length of the embargo may vary between publishers and journals. Requirements from funding agencies or possibilities opened by national laws may also come into play.

REP-04: Articles deposited in an open access repository may be subject to an embargo imposed by the publisher.

Correct answer : TRUE

In France, the Law for a Digital Republic limits this embargo to 6 months for STMs and 12 months for social sciences and humanities.

REP-05: In which search engines are publications deposited in the open access repository Oskar indexed?

Organization-specific question

A) Google Scholar

B) Babord+

C) ResearchGate

Correct answer : A) Google Scholar and B) Babord+

The open access repository Oskar is also indexed by other search engines not listed here.

REP-06: What is the difference between the "Author Accepted Manuscript" (or postprint) and the "Version of Record" (or "published version" or "publisher's" PDF) of an article?

A) Peer review has not been carried out

B) Final publisher's page layout has not been completed

Correct answer: B) Final publisher's page layout has not been completed

The non peer reviewed version of an article is a "preprint" or "submitted manuscript".

REP-07: In France, a researcher can deposit the postprint version of his article in open access in open archive platform repository, regardless of the copyright agreement signed with the publisher.

Correct answer : TRUE

The Law for a Digital Republic of 2016 stipulates this and takes precedence over the conditions set out in the copyright agreement signed with a publisher..

REP-08: On your ResearchGate profile, what situations are always allowed?

A) Mentioning the bibliographic reference of one of your publications

B) Uploading the PDF of your last publication

Correct answer : A) Mentioning the bibliographic reference of one of your publications

Scientific publishers do not necessarily allow articles published in their journals to be posted online via commercial services such as ResearchGate.

REP-09: What do Oskar (or HAL) and ResearchGate (or Academia.edu) have in common?

A) The articles you deposit are freely accessible to all

B) All these systems enable you to comply with the open access requirements of funding agencies

C) You can easily export publication lists from these services

Correct answer : A) The articles you deposit are freely accessible to all

ResearchGate and Academia.edu are commercial services and not open access repositories meeting a number of technical criteria (interoperability, long-term archiving, etc.). The open access requirements of funding agencies include archiving in an open access repository. Have you tried exporting a list of publications from ResaerchGate?

REP-10: The HAL open access repository allows you to generate a personal web page in which the list of publications is updated automatically.

Correct answer : TRUE

HAL allows you to create a multilingual and personalized online CV, in which the list of your publications is automatically updated.

Preprints

5 questions prefixed PRE

PRE-01: What is the "preprint" version of an article?

- A) The first version of an article submitted to a journal for review
- B) The final version of an article posted online before it is included in a journal issue
- C) An offprint

Correct answer : A) The first version of an article submitted to a journal for review

PRE-02: Some publishers impose the use of one preprint platform rather than another.

Correct answer : TRUE

Lancet (owned by Elsevier) has had a partnership since 2018 with SSRN (owned by Elsevier).

PRE-03: A preprint always ends up being published as an article in a scientific journal.

Correct answer : FALSE

PRE-04: Journals systematically refuse to publish an article if a non-peer-validated version has been distributed on a preprint server.

Correct answer : FALSE

The trend is rather the opposite: many publishers do not care about or even encourage the publication of preprints.

PRE-05: PubMed indexes preprints.

Correct answer : TRUE

Coverage is defined by the NIH Preprint Pilot and includes only:

- preprints from NIH-funded research,
- deposited in defined eligible platforms,
- on Covid (2020-2022) or any other topic (2023-...).

See: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/about/nihpreprints/> ; eligible platforms are : bioRxiv, medRxiv, arXiv et Research Square.

Copyright

7 questions prefixed COP

COP-01: You can add an addendum to the standard copyright agreement suggested by a publisher to preserve your rights, such as the right to republish in open access.

Correct answer : TRUE

However, this addendum must be accepted by both parties. There are models for this, particularly in the context of the Rights Retention Strategy.

COP-02: To publish in open access, you do not need to obtain the agreement of your co-authors.

Correct answer : FALSE

Open access or not, the agreement of the co-authors is required for all choices that are made for a joint publication.

COP-03: Publishing under a Creative Commons (CC) license allows the author to set the rules for using his work.

Correct answer : TRUE

This is one of the objectives of CC licenses: to allow the author to define in advance the conditions of reuse of his works.

COP-04: By choosing to publish your article under a Creative Commons (CC) license, you completely waive your rights on your publication.

Correct answer : FALSE

With CC licenses, you waive part of your rights but not, for example, the right to be cited.

COP-05: Which of these is not an option in the Creative Commons (CC) licenses?

- A) Attribution - BY
- B) Use only for research - RO (research only)
- C) Non-commercial use - NC (non-commercial)

Correct answer : B) Use only for research - RO (research only)

"RO (research only)" would be similar to a form of "Fair use" but does not exist.

COP-06: What permissions are granted by the Creative Commons CC-BY license?

- A) The article can only be reused by its author
- B) The article can be reused by anyone, as long as the author is properly cited

Correct answer : B) The article can be reused by anyone, as long as the author is properly cited

One of the objectives of CC licenses is to encourage the reuse of content, the answer option A) would clearly go against this logic.

COP-07: You want to include in your article a figure derived from an image created for another of your articles. You must first ask permission from the publisher of the journal in which the first article appeared.

Correct answer : TRUE

By signing a copyright agreement with a publisher, you might have lost your right to use the content of your own work. Even if you are the author, you should check to what extent this agreement allows you to use your content in your other publications.

Funder policies

6 questions prefixed POL

POL-01: The ANR funds the costs of article processing charges (APC) in fully open access journals, "gold open access".

Correct answer : TRUE

These costs are eligible. However, APC in hybrid journals are not covered.

POL-02: The European Union prefers for researchers to publish their work using the golden open access route, i.e. open access journals.

Correct answer : FALSE

The European Union leaves the choice as to how to publish in open access.

POL-03: Since 2022, what is the maximum embargo period allowed by the ANR before an article is made freely available in an open archive?

- A) No embargo allowed
- B) 6 months
- C) 12 months

Correct answer : A) No embargo allowed

Open access must now be immediate. Both the ANR and the European Union previously allowed a 6-month embargo for STMs and 12 months for social sciences and humanities, but the new ANR2022 and Horizon Europe funding programs have changed this aspect.

POL-04: What types of publications are covered by the European Union's open access requirements?

- A) Conference proceedings
- B) Journal articles
- C) Books and book chapters

Correct answer : B) Journal articles and C) Books and book chapters

Open access requirements apply to all peer reviewed scientific publications.

POL-05: French funding agencies all have different requirements in terms of open access.

Correct answer : FALSE

The French research funding agencies, ADEME, ANR, ANRS-MIE, ANSES, and INCa, have formed a network of exchanges and defined a concerted approach in favor of open science.

POL-06: What is the Rights Retention Strategy?

- A) Another French bureaucratic invention to make life difficult for researchers
- B) A joint international initiative by funding agencies to ensure that authors retain their rights to their articles
- C) A way for funding agencies to ensure that all scientific publications they fund can be reused as widely as possible

Correct answer : B) A joint international initiative by funding agencies to ensure that authors retain their rights to their articles and C) A way for funding agencies to ensure that all scientific publications they fund can be reused as widely as possible

This strategy has been defined within the framework of the PlanS supported by the CoalitionS, which brings together funding agencies from all over the world, at different levels. It applies, for example, to projects funded by the ANR from the 2022 calls for projects and to projects funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme.